

Enhancing Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution Reaction on Ru-Decorated TiO₂ Nanotube Layers: Synergistic Role of Ti³⁺, Ru Single Atoms, and Ru Nanoparticles

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Synergistic interplays involving multiple active centers originating from TiO₂ nanotube layers (TNT) and ruthenium (Ru) species comprising of both single atoms (SAs) and nanoparticles (NPs) augment the alkaline hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) by enhancing Volmer kinetics from rapid water dissociation and improving Tafel kinetics from efficient H* desorption. Atomic layer deposition of Ru with 50 process cycles results in a mixture of Ru SAs and 2.8 ± 0.4 nm NPs present on TNT layers, and it emerges with the highest HER activity among all the electrodes synthesized. A detailed study of the Ti and Ru species using different high-resolution techniques confirmed the presence of Ti³⁺ states and the coexistence of Ru SAs and NPs. With insights from literature, the role of Ti³⁺, appropriate work functions of TNT layers and Ru, and the synergistic effect of Ru SAs and Ru NPs in improving the performance of alkaline HER were elaborated and justified. The aforementioned characteristics led to a remarkable performance by having 9 mV onset potentials and 33 mV dec⁻¹ of Tafel slopes and a higher turnover frequency of 1.72 H₂ s⁻¹ at 30 mV. Besides, a notable stability from 28 h staircase chronopotentiometric measurements for TNT@Ru surpasses TNT@Pt in comparison.

1. Introduction

H₂ is considered an ideal next-generation fuel. Raising greenhouse gas emissions, due to the deployment of fossil fuels in methane reforming and coal gasification, encouraged the electrochemical water splitting as the most reliable method for the green H₂ production. Water electrolysis can be performed in both acidic and alkaline electrolytes. The lower diffusivity of H₂ over the alkaline separator in an alkaline electrolyzer compared to Nafion used in an acid electrolyzer signifies the importance of industrial scale development of catalysts for alkaline electrocatalysis.^[1] Among the developed electrocatalysts, platinum (Pt) is considered to be one of the best electrocatalyst.^[2] However, considering the higher costs incurred and the poor alkaline stability aspects, the search for alternative materials is of great interest.^[3–5] As an alternative material, ruthenium (Ru) has attracted much attention considering its outstanding efficiency and stability for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER).^[6–9] The

development of synergistic hybrid catalysts comprising a robust support loaded with efficient electrocatalysts with high activity and stability for alkaline HER is crucial for the widespread application of water electrolysis for practical H₂ production.

Catalyst supports have high significance to firmly fix the catalyst and backing with an active role in reaction under consideration. Loading catalysts on an appropriate substrate/support can alter the electronic structure of catalysts and thus greatly enhance the catalytic performance.^[10–12] In general, large surface area, anchoring sites, and conductive platforms are considered when choosing a catalytic support. Furthermore, for alkaline water reduction, several studies focused on the aspect of water dissociation, primarily Volmer step to increase the available H* (H* represents adsorbed H at the active site *) in the vicinity of the catalyst.^[13]

Among such widely studied supports is reduced TiO₂, developed in several forms such as thin films,^[14] nanofibers,^[15,16] nanoparticles,^[17] and nanotube layers.^[18] Reports on the loading of Ru NPs on the surface of TiO₂ nanoparticles show an onset potential of 15 mV for alkaline HER arising from the synergistic enhancement of water

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dissociation and the weakening of OH adsorption by reduced TiO₂ NPs.^[19] Several reports indicate that the Ti³⁺ available on the surface of reduced TiO₂ promotes mainly alkaline water dissociation^[13,20,21] resulting in the generation of H* and OH species. The adsorbed H* will be involved in the Heyrovsky or Tafel reaction on an electrocatalyst and will desorb as molecular H₂.^[13] A relatively high work function of a substrate compared to a loaded catalyst is considered to play an important role in the progress of a facile H* spillover leading to efficient H₂ evolution. The lower the difference in the work function of the substrate to the catalyst, the better is the envisioned phenomenon of H* spillover.^[22] The work function of hydroxylated and reduced TiO₂ is approximately around 4.9 and 5.1 eV,^[23] respectively. The estimated work function of the Ru deposited by atomic layer deposition (ALD) was found to be around 4.84 ± 0.1 eV.^[24] For the combination of TiO₂ nanotube (TNT) layers and Ru, the closeness and appropriately positioned work functions can boost the H* spillover and thus enhance the evolution of H₂.

Recent studies show considerable interest in the development of catalysts with a composite of SAs and NPs for their applications in catalytic conversion reactions.^[25–33] An observed enhancement related to the HER is due to a mutually shared Volmer and Heyrovsky or Tafel reaction steps on different species (SAs and NPs) of the catalyst. Considerable interest was devoted to understanding the role of Ru SAs and Ru NPs in aspects of water dissociation and H₂ desorption steps, but no clarity was achieved. Based on first-principles calculations, a low kinetic barrier for dissociation of water from Ru SAs loaded on carbon was responsible for HER in the alkaline electrolyte.^[34] In some instances, the role of water dissociation was associated with Ru NPs on carbon supports.^[12] A faster dissociation of water was associated with Ru NPs having a mean diameter of ~2.37 nm on carbon supports.^[35] The DFT simulations suggest that Ru_{fcc}-oriented NPs on nitrogen-doped carbon supports possess a low energy barrier for water dissociation and thus have better HER activity in alkaline medium.^[36]

Recent studies employing controlled experimental and theoretical studies reveal insights on water dissociation on Ru SAs and further spillover aids in H* adsorption and desorption on Ru NPs.^[26] TiO₂ support for SAs and NPs was also evaluated for different catalytic conversion reactions.^[28] The current manuscript adopts TNT layers as supports and is deposited with Ru species comprising SAs and NPs to enhance the performance for alkaline HER. Here, ALD was employed to decorate the TNT layers with Ru SAs and NPs. The shared roles for water dissociation to produce H*, and H* desorption as H₂ incrementally improved the activity, revealing an onset potential of 9 mV and a Tafel slope of 33 mV dec⁻¹. The nature of the substrate supported an effective anchoring of Ru SAs and NPs, thus leading to a remarkable stability.

2. Results and Discussion

The TNT layers were employed as substrates, as they are known to have abundant OH moieties and defects on their surface that can effectively act as highly efficient nucleation centers.^[37–39] ALD depositions were executed for number of ALD cycles (N_{ALD}) of 6, 12, 25, 50, 100, and 200 on TNT layers. The samples were labeled as TNT Xc Ru, where “X” defines N_{ALD}. The SEM images (Figure S1, Supporting Information) reveal a high density of NPs from 50 N_{ALD}. With a further increase in N_{ALD} to 100, the agglomeration of NPs intensifies. An additional increase in N_{ALD} to 200 develops a continuous layer of Ru. For reference, the ALD process of Pt was also carried out with N_{ALD} of 12, 25,

and 50. A fast nucleation can be visualized for N_{ALD} 12 and further increase in N_{ALD} to 25 and 50 leads to agglomeration of NPs and formation of a continuous Pt thin films (Figure S2, Supporting Information), respectively. Similar Ru ALD nucleation and growth have recently been demonstrated on other substrates as well, such as carbon substrates^[9] and silicon.^[40,41]

The XRD patterns of the Ru deposited with N_{ALD} 25, 50, 100, and 200 are shown in Figure S3, Supporting Information. The data revealed that the characteristic diffraction peaks of the hexagonal crystal phase (hcp) Ru indexed from PDF: 00-06-0663 start to develop from an N_{ALD} of 100. There is an increase in the intensity of the 100% intensity peak (101) (2θ = 44.00) with a further increase in N_{ALD} to 200, which signifies a higher content of Ru. XRD patterns for Pt with N_{ALD} 12, 25, and 50 were also obtained and are provided in Figure S4, Supporting Information. The Pt has a cubic crystal system indexed from PDF: 98-018-0880, with an observed increase in peak intensities with an increasing N_{ALD}.

An insight into the samples with atomic-scale detail was obtained by using transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Scanning TEM imaging with a high-angle annular dark-field (STEM-HAADF) of TNT 50c Ru sample in Figure 1a provides a clear overview of the distribution of uniform-sized NPs on the surface of the TNTs with an average size of 2.8 ± 0.4 nm. The appearance of SAs of Ru together with NP on the surface of the TNT layer for N_{ALD} of 6, 25, and 50 can be seen in Figure S5a–c, Supporting Information. The particle size distribution for TNT 50c Ru is presented in Figure S5d, Supporting Information. The observations suggested that the appearance of Ru SAs on a free surface of TNTs is more frequent for the lower N_{ALD}. After the higher N_{ALD}, the distance between Ru NPs is narrower, which affects the stability of free standing SAs that tend to interact and agglomerate to form NPs. High-resolution aberration-corrected TEM (HR-TEM) image in Figure 1b shows a single Ru NP laying on the surface of a TNT. A fast Fourier transformation (FFT) pattern of this image is available in Figure 1c. Marked spots in the FFT correspond to hcp Ru lattice planes (11̄20) and (1010) with d-spacings of 0.135 and 0.234 nm, respectively. The elemental distribution measurement in Figure 1d–h was performed by a combination of STEM-HAADF imaging coupled with STEM energy-dispersive X-ray (STEM-EDX) spectroscopy. The capability of the developed ALD process in the successful decoration of TNT layers with Ru NPs, in particular the interiors and exteriors of the nanotubes, can be seen from the distributed Ru NPs in the overlay in Figure 1h, suggesting highly conformal and continuous Ru depositions.

In order to have a qualitative insight of the Ru amount deposited on the TNT layers, SEM-EDX and ED XRF analyses were performed for N_{ALD} 6, 12, 25, 50, and 100. These techniques were intentionally chosen, as they are nondestructive elemental analysis methods based on subvalence electron spectrometry. They differ in their sensitivity to elements of various atomic masses and in the depth of the material, from which the analytical signal is obtained, thus providing complementary information about the sample composition. The results are displayed together in Figure S6, Supporting Information. As one can see, there is a clear trend of increasing Ru mass with the increasing number of ALD cycles for both types of measurements, which are thus in a great correlation together.

XPS analysis was performed on control samples, that is, a blank TNT layer and a TNT layer with O₂ and H₂ treatment, and on the main sample, that is, on a TNT layer with Ru decoration. The treatment with O₂ and H₂ was carried out to evaluate the impact of such treatment on the available Ti³⁺ states in the TNT layers. The surface chemical state of the

Figure 1. TEM analysis: STEM-HAADF analysis of TNT 50c Ru showing a) Ru NP distribution on the TNT layer surface, b) an isolated Ru NP on a TNT layer fragment by HR-TEM, and c) corresponding FFT analysis, d) STEM-HAADF image, and e–h) STEM-EDX elemental mapping of Ru decorated single TNT tube: e) Ti-K, f) O-K, g) Ru-L, and h) overlaid maps of O, Ti, and Ru.

blank TNT layer with O₂ and H₂ treatment and Ru-deposited TNT layers was determined (Figure 2a–c). Ti 2p high-resolution spectrum of blank TNT layer after being treated with O₂ and H₂ (Figure 2a) show its spin-orbit splitting Ti 2p_{3/2} and Ti 2p_{1/2}. The curve fitting was performed using six components, which correspond with three different chemical environments. The first doublet (orange) centered at 458.9 and 464.6 eV corresponds to Ti⁴⁺ from the TNT layer.^[42–44] The second doublet (violet) located at 457.7 and 463.4 eV was associated with the existence of Ti³⁺ species in the TiO₂ lattice.^[42–44] The third doublet (pink) at 460.0 and 465.7 eV was assigned to the interaction between F and Ti (Ti-F),^[42,43] related to the electrolyte used during the TNT layers synthesis.

Figure 2b displays the high-resolution spectrum of Ti 2p from the TNT 50c Ru sample. Here, the strong overlapping between Ti 2p and Ru 3p (Ru 3p_{3/2}) signals is evidenced. The curve fitting was performed considering the spin-orbit splitting of both (Ti 2p_{3/2}/Ti 2p_{1/2} and Ru 3p_{3/2}/Ru 3p_{1/2}). Besides, the Ru 3p should have the same chemical species as the Ru 3d, represented in both spectra by the same colors. Twelve components were used, six for Ti 2p, in which there are two different chemical species and a pair of satellite peaks. The other six for Ru 3p, representing three different chemical species. The orange peaks obtained at 458.9/464.6 eV were attributed to the Ti⁴⁺ species from the TNT layers.^[42–44] The violet peaks at 457.7/463.4 eV were related to the Ti³⁺ in the TiO₂ lattice.^[42–44] The green peaks correspond to the Ti 2p satellite signals at 472.8/478.5 eV. The red peaks appear at 461.4/483.8 and are related to Ru⁰ (metallic). The blue peaks located at 462.4/484.8 eV correspond to Ru⁴⁺, and finally, the olive peaks centered at 464.2/486.6 eV were related to Ru⁶⁺.

In Figure 2c, the Ru 3d XPS high-resolution spectrum is shown. The spectrum exhibits a strong overlapping between C 1s and Ru 3d. The spin-orbit splitting Ru 3d_{5/2} and Ru 3d_{3/2} is evidenced, being the latter signal the one strongly overlapped with C 1s. The peak fitting was done using 10 components. Six components are from the Ru spin-orbit splitting, which corresponds to three different chemical species. The remaining four are related to different C contributions. The first doublet

(red) at 280.4 and 284.5 confirms the presence of metallic Ru (Ru⁰).^[9,45,46] The second doublet (blue) was assigned to Ru⁴⁺ evidencing a possible interaction with O at 281.2 and 285.4 eV.^[9,47] The third doublet (olive) was associated with Ru⁶⁺ at ~282.9 and 287.0 eV,^[9,48] which is related to the interaction between the Ru with the atmospheric O or with C and/or O from the substrate during the ALD process. The purple peak at 285.0 eV corresponds to C-(C,H), adventitious carbon.^[49] The orange, violet, and dark yellow peaks at ~286.5, 288.0, and 289.2 eV were assigned to C-O, C=O, and (C=O)-OH, respectively.^[50] The survey spectra from the blank TNT layer, the TNT layer treated with O₂ and H₂, and TNT 50c Ru are provided in Figure S7, Supporting Information.

A STEM combined with the electron energy-loss spectroscopy (STEM-EELS) was performed to qualitatively verify surface oxidation of Ru NPs. STEM-EELS analysis from Figure 2d,e reveals a distribution of individual elements of Ti, O, and Ru and shows several Ru NPs on top of a TNT. The distribution of O and Ru clearly signifies the presence of a native oxide shell developed on Ru NPs, which supports the hypothesis that a maximum amount of nonmetallic oxidation states of Ru observed from XPS arises due to oxidation by atmospheric exposure. The bonding of single atoms of Ru on substrate active sites results in positive charge over the Ru single atoms rather than conventional “0” charge on metallic Ru (Ru-Ru).^[51] Therefore, we also hypothesize that the availability of SAs of Ru contributes to a fraction of observed non-metallic Ru oxidation state. A representative line scan (Cyan in color) (Figure 2d,e) from STEM-EELS confirms the elemental distribution (Figure 2f), supporting an increase in the O concentration, as the line scan reaches the edge of an Ru NP.

Figure 3a shows the linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) results from samples of Ru-decorated TNT layers. The observation from the activity profile (−0.8 to −1.4 V vs. Ag/AgCl) of LSV suggests that all samples have an excellent performance for the HER in alkaline medium. The onset potentials of the samples were 15, 9, 13, and 14 mV for 25, 50, 100, and 200 cycles of Ru, respectively. In general, the footprint of SAs compared to that of NPs can be increased by lowering the number of

Figure 2. XPS high-resolution spectral analyses of: a) Ti 2p of TNT layer treated with O₂ and H₂; b) Ru 3p + Ti 2p of TNT 50c Ru; c) Ru 3d + C 1s of d) TNT 50c Ru. e) STEM-HAADF image of TNT 50c Ru, f) STEM-EELS mapping of TNT 50c Ru providing overlapped distribution from Ti, Ru, and O, corresponding line scan providing the graphical distribution of the elements.

ALD cycles. An increase in the available Ru SAs compared to Ru NPs results in samples obtained with a lower number of ALD cycles. For this reason, 6 and 12 cycles of Ru ALD were performed and a much lower onset potential of 167 and 30 mV, respectively, was observed compared to TNT 25c and 50c Ru (Figure S8, Supporting Information). This suggests that having a higher proportion of SAs is not optimal for high activity. In contrast, higher number of ALD cycles increases the proportion of NPs. The 100 ALD cycles of Ru have a higher proportion of NPs and resulted in an increase in overpotentials compared to the best TNT 50c Ru. The electrocatalytic activities were in most of the cases therefore higher than for TNT 50c Pt with an onset potential of 14.6 mV. The Tafel slope analysis was performed within a decade current density range of 10–100 mA cm⁻². The calculated Tafel slopes were 34, 33, 30, and 28 mV dec⁻¹ for TNT 25, 50, 100, and 200 c Ru, respectively (Figure 3b) compared to 43 mV dec⁻¹ for TNT 50c Pt.

According to the slopes observed from Tafel analysis, the reaction proceeds via the Volmer-Tafel mechanism for Ru-loaded TNT layers. It is noteworthy that, for a complete electrocatalytic comparison, we investigated also TNT layers with 12 and 25 c of Pt ALD processes. However, the electrocatalytic performance was very similar (results not shown here). Therefore, only TNT 50 c Pt samples were investigated in detail in all subsequent electrochemical analyses.

The charge transfer kinetics for HER in alkaline medium was evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), as shown in Figure 3c. Nyquist EIS plots were recorded at an overpotential of 24 mV. A small incomplete semicircle for all the samples at higher frequencies relates to the porous structure of the support (the TNT layers) and is not related to the HER activity of the sample.^[52] All Ru samples, along with Pt, exhibited a prominent semicircle, suggesting that no competing electrochemical process other than HER was involved. The diameter of the semicircle represents the equivalent charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}). R_{ct} values for the samples were 2.62, 2.58, 2.88, and 3.37 Ω for TNT 25, 50, 100, and 200c Ru, respectively. The R_{ct} from EIS results support the low onset potential observed for the TNT 50c Ru sample. Figure 3d represents a comparative bar chart, indicating the overpotentials to obtain 10 mA cm⁻² and the corresponding Tafel slopes from the samples of TNT layers @Ru and TNT layers @Pt.

For HER in an alkaline medium, the dissociation of H₂O to supply H* is one of the rate-limiting steps, responsible for the sluggish kinetics of HER. TNT layers @Ru support faster Volmer kinetics having a combination of Ti³⁺ and Ru SA, as evidenced by XPS and STEM-HAADF analysis.^[13,26] The relative work functions of the TNT layer substrate and the Ru catalyst support a facile spillover of the adsorbed H* to the Ru NPs in the vicinity.^[22] The desorption of H* as molecular H₂ will be supported by densely distributed Ru NPs available on TNT layers.^[26] The phenomenon described above is the most suitable for the observed low onset potentials suggesting the employability of TNT layers as a support for Ru SAs and NPs benefits the alkaline HER performance. Observed low overpotentials (9 mV vs RHE) with a low R_{ct} (2.58 Ω) define TNT 50c Ru as the best among all the prepared samples.

The active electrochemical surface area (ECSA) is a parameter that defines the number of active sites present in a given unit geometric area of the working electrode. The turnover frequency (TOF) is described as the product formed (H₂ in the present case) on a single active site per unit time. Thus, TOF represents an intrinsic activity at each active site of the catalyst. The current density normalized by ECSA is defined as specific activity. In this work, TOF and specific activity were provided at 30 mV. In ideal conditions, a catalyst having a high ECSA with a high

Figure 3. Electrochemical analyses for TNT layers @Ru and TNT layers @Pt: a) Linear sweep voltammograms, b) corresponding Tafel analysis, c) Electrochemical impedance analysis along with the equivalent circuit employed for fitting and d) a comparative evaluation of onset potentials with Tafel slopes.

TOF is desirable. Having these two parameters inversely related, the product of these two defines the activity (current densities) of a catalyst based on the equations provided in the Supporting Information.

The specific activity and the corresponding ECSA (Cu_{upd}) analyses are provided in **Figure 4a**. There is a clear inverse relationship observed with ECSA and specific activity. The calculated $ECSA_{Cu_{upd}}$ are 3.8, 55.95, 34.28, and 16.8 cm^2 for TNT 25, 50, 100, and 200c Ru, respectively. The calculated number of active sites for the Ru samples was 3.8E9, 7.3E16, 3.4E10, and 1.7E10 for TNT 25c, 50c, 100c, and 200c Ru, respectively, supporting the observed trend of ECSA. The trend observed from active area and number of active sites for different samples of TNT layers @Ru collaborates with the onset potentials from LSV. The intrinsic activity of the active sites was evaluated from TOF analyses. A systematic evaluation of TOF at different overpotentials is

Figure 4. a) Comparison of specific activity and electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) calculated and realized employing Cu_{upd} measurements, b) comparison of TOF at different overpotentials.

presented in **Figure 4b**. The calculated TOF for TNT 50c Ru (**Figure 4b**) at an overpotential of 30 mV was $1.74 H_2 s^{-1}$, while for TNT 50c Pt, the TOF was $0.43 H_2 s^{-1}$ (**Figure 4b**) signifying higher intrinsic activity for TNT 50c Ru over TNT 50c Pt. Overall, it is clear from **Figure 4** that the largest specific activity and highest TOF values are achieved for the TNT 25c Ru samples. However, when considering the ECSA, which for HER is an even more important parameter, the most optimal samples in terms of the interplay between TOF, specific activity, and ECSA are the TNT 50c Ru samples. Given the fact that (unfortunately) the number of active sites is a variable number from an experimental point of view (i.e., it is a function of ALD cycles and number and size of Ru SAs and NPs), we consider this chosen interplay comparison, yielding 50c Ru samples as the best from all tested samples, as the most correct way to evaluate the obtained data.

The ECSAs for Ru noble metal electrocatalysts were evaluated by Cu underpotential deposition (Cu_{upd}) analyses. The term “Under potential deposition” is referred to as potential required for electrodeposition of monolayer of a low work function metal on a foreign metal surface with higher work function.^[53] **Figure S9**, Supporting Information, represents Cu_{upd} for TNT 50c Ru and TNT 50c Pt, respectively. A careful consideration of the initial polarization potential to realize underpotential deposition of Cu was performed and represented in **Figure S9**, Supporting Information, where a clear indication of the polarization potential with respect to bulk Cu deposition (electrodeposition on the same metal surface) and monolayer deposition (electrodeposition on higher work function metal) on TNT 50c Ru is verified. Thus, the polarization potential was fixed to 0.220 V for the development of a Cu_{upd} , and the same potential was employed for rest of the samples of TNT layers @Ru. **Figure S10**, Supporting Information, shows Cu_{upd} stripping plots from TNT 25, 50, 100, and 200c Ru samples.

The electrochemical stability for TNT 50c Ru compared to TNT 50c Pt is presented in **Figure 5**. The staircase chronopotentiometry shown in **Figure 5a** for TNT 50c Ru and TNT 50c Pt at different current densities of 10, 20, 50, and 100 and 10 $mA cm^{-2}$ was maintained for 4 h each until 100 $mA cm^{-2}$ and in the final for 12 h (10 $mA cm^{-2}$). The stable performance of TNT@Ru can be seen in **Figure 5b** LSV before and after prolonged stability measurements compared to TNTs layers @Pt (**Figure 5c**). The change in onset potentials were 3 and 21 mV for TNTs layers @Ru and TNTs layers @Pt, respectively. The TNT 50c Ru outperforms TNT 50c Pt considerably in the chronopotentiometric stability tests. In general, limited Pt stability could arise from leaching, agglomeration, detachment, or separation of Pt from the support, when the stability was tested.^[54] However, due to the nature of ALD

Figure 5. Stability analysis: a) chronopotentiometric (CP) measurements for TNT 50c Ru and TNT 50c Pt; LSV curves before and after stability for b) TNT 50c Ru, c) TNT 50c Pt, respectively, d) for TNT 50c Ru before and after accelerated degradation tests.

processing, we can rule out any detachment issues for either Pt or Ru species. It is more the difference in the chemical resistance, which is higher for Ru. This supports the idea that the Ru electrocatalyst (on TNT layers supports) - developed by employing ALD - is highly stable in an alkaline electrolyte. The samples of TNT 50 Ru after stability were analyzed by XPS and TEM (Figures S11 and S12, Supporting Information). Post-mortem studies from XPS confirmed a slight increase of nonmetallic Ru originating from either prolonged exposure to atmosphere or alkaline KOH employed (Table S1, Supporting Information). A 0.65% impurity linked to barium was observed, whose origin was not assertive. TEM post-mortem studies confirm that the TNT 50c Ru samples were morphologically stable and robust.

As an alternative stability measurement, accelerated degradation tests were performed in a potential range of ± 50 mV at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} for 2500 cycles. The results of Figure 5d authenticate that the TNT 50c Ru performs exceptionally well with a very low change in the onset potential of 5.6 mV between before and after the degradation tests.

3. Conclusion

In summary, a robust and reliable ALD process was developed and employed to decorate Ru SAs and NPs on TNT layers. The functional groups and defects available on the TNT layers supported the development of uniform and conformal Ru decoration consisting of SAs and NPs with a size of $2.8 \pm 0.4 \text{ nm}$ for TNT 50c Ru. The samples developed from TNT 50c Ru exhibited a superior alkaline HER with an exceptionally low onset potential of 9 mV to deliver a benchmark current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} and a low Tafel slope of 33 mV dec^{-1} .

The calculated TOF of TNT 50c Ru was $1.74 \text{ H}_2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at an overpotential of 30 mV and was four times higher than TNT 50c Pt. The activity enhancement was correlated with the presence of Ti^{3+} , Ru SAs, and Ru NPs and having reliable work function values from the TiO_2 support to Ru. Ti^{3+} and Ru SAs support Volmer reaction, and Ru NPs support Tafel reaction, and close the work functions TNT layers to Ru, supporting the H^* spillover. The robust nature of the TNT layers support and exceptional prospects of the Ru catalyst aided the extremely stable catalyst in nature, as observed from chronopotentiometry and accelerated degradation tests of the TNT 50c Ru that surpasses TNT 50c Pt in comparison. This work emphasizes the high significance of robust and high surface area TNT layers with Ru SAs and NPs offering cooperative multicomponent active sites to boost alkaline HER and reinforced with ultra-stable long-term stability, and furthermore, the robustness of the electrode allows forecast applications under high pressure conditions as well.

4. Experimental Section/Methods

Materials: KOH (Penta), CuSO_4 (Penta), Bis(ethylcyclopentadienyl)ruthenium(II), 98% (99.9%-Ru) (Strem Europe), Ti foil ($127 \mu\text{m}$ thick, 99.7%, Sigma-Aldrich), NH_4F (Sigma-Aldrich), Ethylene glycol (anhydrous, Sigma-Aldrich).

TNT layers fabrication and Ru ALD deposition: TNT layers were prepared via anodization of Ti foil in an ethylene glycol-based electrolyte, containing 150 mM NH_4F and 10 vol% H_2O .^[55] The anodization was carried out at a potential of 100 V for 4 h, using a high-voltage potentiostat (PGU-200V, IPS Elektronik-labor GmbH). Thus, the prepared TNT layers were $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ thick with a nanotube diameter of $\sim 230 \text{ nm}$. After anodization, the TNT layers were rinsed and sonicated in isopropanol and dried in air. As as-prepared TNT layers are amorphous, prior to further use, they were annealed in a muffle oven at 400°C for 1 h (sweeping rate: $2.1^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) to receive anatase phase. ALD processes with different cycles of Ru and Pt were performed on TNT layers.

The ALD was performed using the BENEQ TFS 200 thermal reactor with the stop-flow configuration. Ru deposition on the TNT layers was carried out using bis(ethylcyclopentadienyl)ruthenium(II) ($\text{Ru}(\text{EtCp})_2$) as Ru precursor, and oxygen (O_2) and H_2 as co-reactants.^[9] The organometallic compound $\text{Ru}(\text{EtCp})_2$ precursor offers a good benefit in tuning the ALD process. A 6N ultra-high purity N_2 was used as purge gas. The container for $\text{Ru}(\text{EtCp})_2$ was held at 90°C and the chamber temperature was kept at 275°C . Gas lines were held around 90°C with proper insulation. During the Ru ALD process, a 1-s pulse of Ru precursor (split into two 500 ms pulses) with 10 s of exposure and 20 s of purge was used. The Ru pulse was followed by an O_2 pulse of 800 ms with 10 s of exposure and 20 s of purge and by a further sequential 1.25 s pulse of H_2 with 10 s of exposure and 20 s of purge, thus oxidizing and sequential reduction of the absorbed Ru to deposit metallic Ru. Thus, each ALD cycle is comprised of sequential $\text{Ru}(\text{EtCp})_2 - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$ components. Each ALD cycle was applied for different numbers of ALD cycles " N_{ALD} ", resulting in metallic Ru species ranging from single atoms to nanoparticles. In this work, four different N_{ALD} of Ru were performed: $N_{\text{ALD}} = 25, 50, 100,$ and 200 cycles. Additional samples of TNT layers with Pt ($N_{\text{ALD}} = 12, 25$ and 50) were deposited following our previous published report.^[56] All samples were named TNT Xc M, where "X" represents N_{ALD} and "M" represents the deposited metal (Ru or Pt).

Characterization: Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analyses were carried out by field-emission SEM JEOL JSM 7500F and image-aberration corrected TEM

Thermo Fisher Scientific TITAN Themis 60–300. The TEM was operated at 120 kV for STEM-EELS and at 300 kV for other measurements. The acquisition EDX and EELS spectra were performed by using Super-X and Gatan Quantum 966 ERS spectrometers, respectively. STEM, EDX, and HR-TEM data were collected and processed with SW Velox; EDX maps were created in form of net intensities of elements of interest. EELS data were collected and processed with SW GMS3.3; EELS maps were created with use of model-based quantification to atomic %. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was carried out using Panalytical Empyrean with Cu tube and Pixcel3D detector. Elemental composition data were obtained using a scanning electron microscope LYRA 3 (Tescan) equipped with EDX analyzer AZtec X-Max 20 (Oxford Instruments). The EDX measurements were performed at 20 kV acceleration voltage on five $400 \times 400 \mu\text{m}$ areas. The EDX results were evaluated in AZtec software (Oxford Instruments). The error bars represent the standard deviation from average values. ED XRF measurements were performed using an Elva X spectrometer (Elvatech, Ukraine) equipped with an Rh tube operated at a voltage of 45 kV. The tube current was stabilized for optimal detector loading, and filter 4 (Ni 300, Al 300) was used to pretreat the excitation beam. The spectrum acquisition time was 120 s, and the measurements were conducted in an air atmosphere. The surface chemical composition of TNT@Ru was determined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, ESCA-2SR, Scienta Omicron). Spectra were recorded using monochromatic Al $K\alpha = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$ X-ray source operated at 250 W. The binding energy scale was referenced to the adventitious carbon (284.8 eV) for the blank TNT samples and to the Fermi level cut-off for TNT 50c Ru samples. CasaXPS software (Casa software Ltd) was used to analyze the data and the quantitative analysis was made using sensitivity factors provided by the manufacturer. Ti 2p spectrum was fitted with Shirley background and a mixed Gaussian–Lorentzian function GL (30). Also, the area ratio and binding energy distance constraints between the spin–orbit splitting (Ti $2p_{3/2}$ and Ti $2p_{1/2}$), 2:1 and 5.7 eV, respectively, were taken into the account. The Ru 3p + Ti 2p spectra fitting was done with Shirley background, all the ruthenium components are asymmetrical; therefore, a Lorentzian–Asymmetric function LA (0.8,3.5,80) was used. Also, the area ratio and binding energy distance constraints between the spin–orbit splitting (Ru $3p_{3/2}$ and Ru $3p_{1/2}$), 2:1 and 22.4 eV, respectively, were taken into the account. For the titanium components, the same conditions of the bare Ti 2p spectrum were used, included in this case the two Ti 2p satellites, since the binding energy window is wide. Ru $3d + C 1s$ spectra were fitted with Shirley background, all the ruthenium components are asymmetrical; therefore, a Lorentzian–Asymmetric function LA (0.8,4.5,80) was used. Also, the area ratio and binding energy distance constraints between the spin–orbit splitting (Ru $3d_{5/2}$ and Ru $3d_{3/2}$), 3:2 and 4.17 eV, respectively, were taken into the account. For the carbon components, a mixed Gaussian–Lorentzian function GL (30) was used.

HER activity measurements: The electrochemical HER measurements were performed using a three-electrode system using AUTOLAB (PGSTAT 204; Metrohm Autolab B. V.; Nova 1.10 software). Ru decorated TNT layers with a geometrical area of 1 cm^2 were used as working electrodes. Graphite rod and a calibrated Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) were used as counter and reference electrodes, respectively. For LSV, a scan rate of 2 mV s^{-1} was employed. A 100% *iR*-correction was performed to evaluate Tafel slopes for all the samples. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed in the frequency range of 0.1–100 kHz with an AC voltage amplitude of 10 mV. All these measurements were carried out at least on three samples of the same type with very good reproducibility obtained.

The active surface area of the catalyst was determined by copper underpotential deposition (Cu_{upd}) method. Cu_{upd} measurements were performed in acidic solutions with a scan rate of 10 mV sec^{-1} having $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and 5 mM CuSO_4 , while the base line was recorded employing $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ electrolyte. To evaluate Cu_{upd} , the electrode was polarized at 0.205, 0.210, 0.215, 0.220, 0.225 V for 100 s followed by an LSV from the polarization potential to 0.8 V in a solution of $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and 5 mM CuSO_4 . During the polarization process at the chosen polarization potential, a monolayer of Cu was formed on the active Ru sites on the surface of TNT layers. The as-formed Cu monolayer was stripped by the following LSV performed from 0.220 to 0.8 V. The area under the peak of Cu stripping represents the charge involved in stripping the deposited Cu monolayer. The baseline to evaluate the charge associated with the stripping of absorbed Cu was obtained by performing a CV from the same solution with no Cu salt added. Stability analyses were performed by chronopotentiometric and accelerated degradation tests in 1 M KOH on a geometric area of 1 cm^2 of the sample. Unless otherwise stated,

all the potentials reported here are with respect to reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE), by converting the potentials measured with respect to Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl). pH for 1 M KOH is considered as 14 for all the calculations.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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